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To Develop Competency in Junior College in Science (Physics) through Rajyoga Meditation Methodology

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Abstract It is better to say changing world rather than developing, as in this 21st century people keep not stone unturn in any field, may it be social media, farming, education, skills etc. thus, now a days everyone has to work upon IQ, EQ and SQ. In the competitive world everyone has to face competition thus education systems have to employ new way of teaching and learning technique. NEP 2020 is also wanting teachers to train the students for competency level, but one thing is noticeable that to build competency somewhere we have reached to initial education system in Bharat. Meditation is one of the finest way to increase the focus, concentration and competency level in an individual. Brahmakumaris Rajyoga Meditation is Bhart ancient meditation technique to build character and personality of a student. The new world is full of technology thus Physics if one of the major subjects which all the competitive exams look for clarity in concepts, creativity in application and calculative risk. Prajapita Brahmakumaris Rajyoga method of teaching enable students of Physics to assimilate the concept and apply them in the hierarchal level to achieve the competency level.

Keywords: Competency, NEP 2020f, Rajyoga method of teaching, Anvikshiki

Introduction

Competency is a word that talks about the potent of a being, but now a days it is not just a word it is metamorphosed into action 21st century world is demanding new skills, practical knowledge, accurate thinking, calculative brain, focused attention, clear vision, powerful mission and of course a holistic person. Education before 5 x decade was just knowledge and knowing named learning, thereafter 2 x decade it became knowing with experience named experiential learning, now everyone says the experience should be used anywhere and everywhere in the world so we named it competency.

The above shloka means “Let us train our mind to be resilient. The mind that does not cripple in adversities, helps to get out of those very calamities. Resilience refers to both the process and the outcome of successfully adapting to difficult or challenging life experiences”.

Correlation between competency and IQ

It is better to say changing world rather than developing, as at the time of transition of grains from one pot to another every grain of the sand has to move and have to move otherwise the grain will not be shifted to the new container, similarly everyone in the 21st century world has to learn and have to learn otherwise you will not be able to walk with the world or else you will seem to be lost always. During vedic age education's role was to build competency thereafter things got shifted to machines and then to technology, now due to incomplete personality traits, education is trying to build IQ + EQ + SQ. without all competency building is not possible. National Journal of Hindu and Sanskrit research (2024), Ms Gauri Hanspal, modern education system will grow the wings to fly high in sky if it starts focusing on character education rather than just education, holistic development rather than just development. Fostering ethics and responsibility, thus we need foundation of oral education system of vedic age enhance students' memory, communication skills, and engagement with the material, making learning a more interactive and dynamic process. Teacher-student relationship can be strengthened through mentorship guidance and support, encouraging students to reach their full potential. Promoting environmental awareness through education. By blending above following aspects of Vedic education with modern teaching methods, we can create a more holistic, values-driven, and sustainable educational system.

Truth in vedic pedagogy of teaching

A famous newspaper Times of India says that, vedic education was destroyed by Britishers through Max Muller and Thomas Macaulay. Both set wrong narrative and wrong perception about vedic education and Bhartiya culture amongst the citizen of the nation. With the aim of introducing English education in India and wanted to make the Indians into a race that was Indian in blood and colour, but English in taste, in opinion, in morals and in intellect. Vedic education aims for character building education and capability building in an individual so that one can contribute to the society by focusing over emotional, intellectual and spiritual development, thus solution of existing problems in the education institutes can only be resolved through vedic education model of teaching. In short one has to focus on IQ, EQ and SQ, in other words head, hard and hands. When IQ test was taken over literacy and numeracy, thus it was found that there is a high impact on numeracy while moderate over literacy, while personality affects literacy more. But by the analysis it is overserved that the effect of personality and IQ over cognition is moderate. Thus, one can build competency by practice and write strategy.

Vedic education system enables us to use four domains of learning collectively

1. Shravan, which means listening your master along with thinking over the same piece of information. It also means knowing and understanding together, as these two process are simultaneous and they follow each other.
2. Chintan, which means after understanding now start using your own thoughts to get the concept clarity. In short, we are dealing with analysis, go back to step 1, but this time remember and understand the things before you apply.
3. Mannan, which means more of abstract while thinking that the individual keeps evaluating along with application.
4. Nididyan, which means creating and putting things in existence.

Measurement of competency in 21st century

If we observe NEP 2020, it is inclined to build values, skill development and holistic development. From the past in mythological history Guru Dronacharya not only taught his Shishyas the theoretical knowledge but also, he created wisdom amongst them for real life. Just knowing things doesn't mean that you are educated. Knowing and understanding along with this using and applying the known things wisely is education, such act is competency. May the resources limited to solve a problem, but wisdom enables the individual to solve the problem and get things done with the available resources. According to PISA (2018) competency is basically to develop skills and efficiency in an individual related to language comprehension, applying logic and creative thinking. PISA has conducted the test to help the governments to understand the condition of education system, thus how are the learners getting prepared for the future! It is even helping the education system for necessary changes, thus enabling all the countries to learn from each other. A online newspaper 'The Wire' gives the data of PISA, that the exam focuses on the application and creative part of the knowledge and not just producing what the learner has learnt in the class room. It aimed to test mathematical skills in the year 2022 after 2003 & 2012. Reading in the year 2000, 2009 & 2018, while scientific temperament in the year 2006 & 2015. PISA is organised by Economic co-operation and Development (OECD) every triennially. PISA tests the skills and knowledge of 15 yrs old students in mathematics, reading and science. In 2009 when India took the assessment it ranked 73rd out of 74 countries. What does this show! Perhaps either the Blooms taxonomy is not used properly or it is not working in our country. Bhartiya genius is made to follow vedic Rajyoga education system, minds with so much of potentiality and creativity needs a way to pour out the talent somewhere for the betterment of the world with the concentrated manner. We Bhartiya are made to learn in our own way. OECD report says reading and science trajectories had been falling for a decade. Today students do not read, rather they try to find an easy way to learn just by just watching the things on YouTube. PISA is a social phenomenon of what a learner has learnt and also a political project when in the countries will come to know the direction of youth creativity.

There is a very famous saying in the army: "Wars are not fought in the battlefield, but in the minds of the generals", thus while training the students Acharya Chanakya has always emphasised on strategic thinking called as Aanvikshiki. It is the science of strategic thinking based on philosophy. Such vedic strategic of better learning is required for the present intensified learning. It is found that in physics there are few minds are addled while applying multiple formulas in the same numerical, while there are few heads who are perplex for many basic concepts. The art of thinking is very much essential in the learning of practical physics. Knowledge is a power, it does not matter who you are and whom you belong to, what matters is the way you use the power. According to Chanakya the best way of learning is play games, you don't play the games for the sake of playing but play it so that you think the strategy and you mind starts thinking. In any game there will be winners and losers, but both can be learners, the one who keeps learning, keeps improving and winning becomes natural for him. Thus, learning has a golden rule, the more you plan during peacetime, the less you bleed during wartime. Planning is more important than execution. In fact, better planning helps in effective execution. Rajyoga method of teaching and learning though connected to spiritual education, but the strategy is coherent to a warfare, the thinking is similar to a king. Rajyoga meditation teaching methodology has four aspects Gyan, Yoga, Dharana and seva. If we go in deep root understanding of the aspect. Gyan is basically acquiring knowledge, which is basic in all subjects and so is in physics too, thereafter is the main role of yoga which means seating quietly reflecting inside about your weakness and strength make the strategy in you mind first to over come your weakness with the help of your strength, thus if we apply it to physics we get to understand that the addled and perplex responses form the students while solving a competency problem will become easy as the learner is actively involved in learning without the teachers support, where the learner is supporting and take owns of him/ her. The learner get to understand self - learning through reflection technique as well able to make strategy to over come learning gap by planning his learning method. Dharna stands for the responsibility of absorbing the learnt material and understanding that learning and then serving the society constructively through the learnt material is seva.

Here the next question arises does learning needs leadership quality or leadership quality is build after learning everything in life!... I feel only a good leader is an excellent learner. A good leader has to do follow many dimensions viz lead people to high goal, dimension of clarity to take right decisions in difficult circumstances, nothing is impossible for such leader, inspiring a group and walking the talk. Leadership is not only knowing the

game but winning the game. Above all it is the ability to see things where others do not. Leadership is not just about a position or power of authority that you hold, it is also being morally right. According to our Indian scriptures, a leader has to be Dharmic first. He has to be righteous, that's why called as Raja – Rishi. Thus, every student may it be boy or a girl, every learner is a leader of his/ her own learning goals. To understand a subject one needs to do three types of reading, rather it read it three times, but from different angles. The first-time reading should be general reading of concepts in physics, almost like taking a glance. During second reading take a pen or a pencil and make the notes, if there are questions, get clarity on them and seek answers from experts. The third type of reading is called revision reading. After clearing all your doubts, you revisit the book. This time you are almost like an expert on the subject. Now, you can also go and give a presentation on the learnt material to others. The right technique of reading means being a reader of a concept in physics, you become a speaker of the concept in physics. For a student of age 15 to 18 years reading and learning physics is no less than understanding an ancient scripture, you require four types of Krupa or grace: Atma Krupa means for learning the concept have mercy on self and motivate self, Ishwar Krupa means learning any constructive material is like worshiping the ocean of knowledge The GOD, Guru Krupa means the concept which you read come and discuss it with your teacher and get more concept clarity for best understanding and the last is Shastra Krupa means for good self- learning good books are mandatory like for good understanding and practicing physics majority students prefer HC Verma, it also means not to speak about the book, but it is the book that has to speak to you. Rajyoga method of teaching learning includes note making, self- reflection, experiencing the learnt material and then apply the experience to the real - life situations. Unlike teachers making their own lesson plan before going to the class the students as well make lesson plan of each chapter, write what have you learnt and write the points of self – audit or reflection points which enables the individual to rectify their mistakes and fill the learning gaps. Quantum leap of performance will only know when you surprisingly test yourself.

Conclusion and Suggestion

If one tries to understand the pattern of learning we will find various forms of learning pattern viz visual, auditory, reading and kinaesthetic, but one thing is common that is basic thinking style. Rajyoga has a main component of development as reflection, which Baba says chart rkho. The Rajyoga style of teaching learning is done through soul power or in another terms training of a soul to use mind in efficient way, thus self-directing, self-guidance after teachers' guidance and meditating to get clear insight. Churning of knowledge so that material is digested easily and then the experience of using the knowledge to others. When all of us were kids, teacher use to play decisive, strategic, earnest, vital and central role in every one's life, teacher's words use to be verdict, but as the time passes the same individual cannot follow the teacher! But why! Have we ever thought of it! It is because of self- low esteem and self -doubts an individual is not able to pay respect to others. When through meditation an individual can rise his or her self- respect, he owes his learning. Rajyoga at Prajapita Brahmakumaris world spiritual university caters four domains for learning and building a good character namely gyan, yoga, dharna and seva for all the subjects may it be language, science or mathematics this technique of teaching learning pedagogy will be effective. Gyan mean knowledge with understanding rather than just knowledge or just understanding yoga meaning an abstract exercise of being with the teacher and teachings mentally and analysing, synthesising, and revising the things which will help an individual for keeping understood material in the memory. Still, we cannot say learnt material. But just understood. Now start applying and evaluating which travels with a motto "check and change" at the end is creating which has the values of seva. Now one can say that learning is done. Just a well class room setup cannot provide the holistic learning. Some slogan can justify the kind and level of teaching practice in Rajyoga, "swaprivarntan se Vishwa Parivartan". Before you help other to uplift charity begins at home.

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